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The Trust in the Service Sector in Europe

Between March and December 2022 it decreased by 66.54%

The Eurostat calculates the value of the trusted index in services. The indicator considers the short-term request for services in Europe. The data are decreased. The period analyzed is between March 2022 and December 2022.

Ranking of European countries for the value of trust in the service sector in December 2022. Greece is in the first place for the value of trust in the service sector with a value of 23.4 units, followed by Turkey with a value of 23 units and from the Czech Republic with a value equal to 20.3 units. In the middle of the standings there are Austria and Finland with a value equal to 2.7 units, followed by Slovakia with a value of 2 units. Poland close the ranking with a value equal to -11.4%, from Estonia with a value equal to -22.8% and from Hungary with an amount equal to -27.1%.

Ranking of European countries by percentage variation of the indicator of trust in the services sector between March 2022 and December 2022. Cyprus is in the first place for the value of the percentage variation of trust in the service sector with a value of 212.3% equal to an amount of 12.1 units, followed by Romania with a value of 84.38% equal to an amount of 2.7 units, and from Bulgaria with a value of 76.27% equal to an amount of 4.5 units. Croatia close the ranking with a value -48.13% equal to an amount of -11.6 units, followed by Malta with a value equal to -50.2% equal to an amount of -12.3 units and from the France with a variation equal to an amount of -62% equal to an amount of -3.1 units. Lithuania closes the ranking with a value equal to -216.7% equal to an amount of -5.2 units, followed by Estonia with a value equal to -356% equal to an amount of -17.8 units and from Hungary equal to a value of -411.3% equal to an amount of -21.8 units.

Clusterization with K-means algorithm. Below is a clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized with the Elbow method. The analysis shows the presence of four Clusters or:

- Cluster 1: Greece, Albania, Turkey, Czech Republic, Slovenia;
- Cluster 2: Sweden, Malta, Ireland, Montenegro, Portugal, Croatia;
- Cluster 3: Netherlands, France, Slovakia, Romania, Germany, Bulgaria, Austria, Denmark, Cyprus, Finland, Belgium, Serbia, Northern Macedonia, Italy, Spain;
- Cluster 4: Poland, Lithuania, Estonia, Hungary, Latvia.

From the point of view of the median, the following system of the Clusters or: $C1 = 20.3 > C2 = 9.05 > C3 = 2 > C4 = -11.4$. From a geographical point of view, it appears that some countries of South-East European have high values of trust in services such as Turkey and Greece; Follow a group of very heterogeneous countries or Portugal, Ireland, Norway. In third place there are most large European countries, followed by Poland and Baltic countries.

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Network Analysis with the use of Manhattan's distance. A Network Analysis is applied below with the use of Manhattan's distance. Three complex network structures are identified. There is a complex network structure composed of these countries or:

- France has a connection with North Macedonia with a value of 0.66 units, and with Romania for a value equal to an amount of 0.56 units;
- Romania has a connection with France for a value of 0.56 units, with North Macedonia equal to an amount of 0.56 units and with Bulgaria for a value of 0.61 units;
- Northern Macedonia has a connection with France for a value of 0.66 units and with Romania for a value of 0.56 units;
- Bulgaria has a connection with Romania equal to an amount of 0.61 units.

There is also a complex network structure composed of the following countries or:

- Finland has a connection with Denmark for a value of 0.75 units;
- Denmark has a connection with Finland for a value of 0.75 units, Coni La Serbia for a value equal to an amount of 0.75 units, with the Netherlands for a value equal to 0.73 units and with Austria for a value of 0.81 units;
- The Netherlands have a connection with Spain for a value of 0.75 units, with the Netherlands equal to an amount of 0.53 units, with Austria for a value of 0.63 units and with Denmark for a value of 0.73 units;
- Spain has a connection with the Netherlands equal to a value of 0.75 units and with Germany for a value of 0.71 units;
- Germany has a connection with Spain for a value of 0.71 units, with the Netherlands for a value of 0.53 units, with Austria for a value of 0.77 units;
- Austria has a connection with the basic countries for a value of 0.63 units, with Germany for a value of 0.77 units, and with Denmark for a value of 0.81 units;
- Serbia has a connection with Denmark for a value of 0.75 units.

There is a complex network structure composed of the following countries or:

- Estonia has a connection with Lithuania for a value of 0.8 units;
- Lithuania has a connection with Estonia for a value of 0.8 units and with Latvia for a value of 0.72 units;
- Latvia has a connection with Lithuania for a value of 0.72 units.

Network Analysis allows you to grasp the effects of propagation of trust in the services sector between the various countries analyzed. For example, if it increases (or decreases) by 1 unit the trust of services in Lithuania then it appears that this trust increases (or decreases) by 0.8 Estonia units and increases (or decreases) by 0.72 Latvia units. This relationship must not be understood as a cause-effect link. This relationship simply indicates a dimension of similarity in the dynamics of the historical series of the countries.

Conclusions. Trust in the service sector in March 2022 was equal to an amount of 10.97 units and decreased in December 2022 up to 3.67 units or a variation of -66.54% equal to -7.30 units. From a temporal point of view, trust in the service sector, on average, grew from March 2022 to May 2022 from 10.97 units up to 17.32. However, starting from May 2022 the average value of the confidence of services has started to decrease up to the absolute minimum of December 2022. Since the services sector tends to be the most relevant among the various economic sectors then, it follows that, A loss of confidence in services is certainly an omen of an economic-financial crisis.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

C1>C2>C3>C4

